
SARANSH WEB PORTAL AND MOBILE APPLICATION FOR CBSE SCHOOL

Mrs. P. Krishnakumari¹ & Dr. R. Sarangapani²

¹Research Scholar, Dept. of Library and Information Science, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu.

²University Librarian & I/c Head, Dept. of Library and Information Science, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu.

Corresponding Author - Mrs. P. Krishnakumari

Email- kumari.bscct@gmail.com

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Abstract:

A CBSE initiative, it is a self-review and analysis tool for CBSE-affiliated schools and parents. It enables them to assess students' performance and implement corrective measures. This allows schools to compare their performance to that of all CBSE schools. It also allows parents to compare their ward's performance at various levels within the school, state, region, and national levels. Saransh allows parents and teachers to have one-on-one conversations about their children's performance and overall growth.

Keywords: Saransh web portal, Mobile application, CBSE School.

Introduction:

Saransh is a web portal created by India's Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). to promote information and communication technologies in schools. In November On July 7, 2015, Human Resource Development Minister Smriti Irani launched the portal. The 'Saransh' is a self-review and analysis tool for CBSE (Central Board of Secondary Education) affiliated schools and students. It enables them to analyze students' performance and implement appropriate corrective measures. The 'Saransh E-School Mobile Application allows students to view their results as well as an overview of their academic performance in grades 10 and 12. The Saransh tool brings together schools, parents, and teachers to track and improve students' progress. It offers a data-driven decision support

system that will help teachers and parents make the best decisions for their student's futures. The Saransh tool enables schools to identify areas for improvement in teachers, students, and the curriculum. By comparing results assists in taking the necessary steps to implement change. It will allow students and parents to compare their school results at the state level and national levels.

Review of Literature:

Das, S (2021) This qualitative study will focus on how, by 2021, private apps and websites, as well as field-specific educational apps, have made digital education essential in India. This also focuses on the online educational economy in 2021. Keeping all of this in mind, this paper enlightens the online education field

via private apps and also reminds us of the measures we should take in the future.

Kumar, S (2021) This paper discussed how digital learning can help in times of crisis, such as absenteeism or epidemics. To that end, some digital learning tools and techniques for ensuring learning continuity are highlighted. The benefits and drawbacks of online learning platforms are also discussed. The perspectives of learners and educators on the Online Learning system during the lockdown are discussed.

Meel, M (2021) To build a thriving knowledge economy, India must utilize this chance this opportunity and make every effort to provide quality education to all strata of society. The paper also discusses the benefits and drawbacks of online platforms.

Sunil M, G (2020) This research aims to examine the new government of India's higher education digital initiatives in recent years, as well as their impact on changes in the modern Indian education system.

Saransh Platform:

Saransh is a tool that allows schools to identify areas for improvement in students, teachers, and curriculum in order to facilitate and implement change. The platform is currently available for classes 9th through 12th, and it provides a standard 10th performance since 2007 and a standard 12th performance from 2009 to the current academic session. Currently, CBSE results are available on this portal/app. Other ICT initiatives featured at the event included the IVR (Interactive Voice Response) system for monitoring the daily implementation of the Mid-Day Meal Scheme and Shaala Darpan, an integrated platform to address all academic

Rani, N (2019) There are tools available today that can transform learning from an academic exercise into an engaging experience in imaginative and experiential learning. Today, ubiquitous and persistent technologies have reshaped the traditional role of the teacher. There have been sporadic and unrelated initiatives to integrate technology into education.

Objective of the Study:

- To discuss the CBSE Saransh web platform and its features.
- To talk about the Saransh E-School Mobile app
- To describe the Saransh GK app.

Research Methodology:

The paper is derived from secondary data or information sources. Various online news reports and government websites to achieve accuracy and intensive evaluation of the study, a descriptive research design is used in consideration of the research objectives.

and administrative needs of schools, teachers, parents, and students.

CBSE has developed an in-house decision support system called "SARANSH" with the goal of "improving children's education." by enhancing interaction between schools and parents and providing a data-driven decision support system to assist them in making the best decisions for their children's future." Saransh is a tool for comprehensive self-review and analysis for CBSE-affiliated schools and parents. It enables them to assess students' performance and take corrective action. Saransh connects schools, teachers, and parents so that they can track students'

progress and help them improve their performance.

Features:

- It is open for classes IX and X, Problem-Solving Abilities (PSA) in classes IX and XI, and Board Exam Achievements in Class XII, and provides a complete comprehensive picture of Class X from 2007 to the most recent academic session.
- It enables schools to examine their performance in scholastic and co-scholastic areas on an aggregate level as well as at the level of each student in the school.
- All evaluation criteria are presented numerically as well as in charts/graphs for easy comprehension. Saransh assists schools in comparing their performance to other schools across India, regionally, and by state, as well as within their school category (Government, Private, Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (JNVS), Kendriya Vidyalaya Sangathan (KVS), and Central Tibetan Schools) (CTS)

Saransh E-School Mobile Application:

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Saransh E-School Mobile Application enables schools to provide all of a child's information to their parents in a timely and cost-effective manner. Saransh app provides the following information to parents: Student Personal Details from School Record, Student Attendance, Transport Details with Stoppage Timings, Weekly Test Results, Results, Home-Work, Curriculum, Teacher Words for Child, Examinations dates, School Calendar with Event Details, Upcoming Competitions, School News, Fees Details, Student Library Account Details

Application of the Saransh App:

Parents of CBSE students can access the Saransh E-School App by following the steps below:

- Saransh is available to parents of all CBSE-affiliated school students in grades 9, 10, 11, and 12.
- Parents can get the Saransh E-School App from the App Store.
- They can use their student's registration/roll number to register on the Saransh App.
- They will receive the username and password via OTP and email on the registered mobile number.

- They can review their students' performance by logging into the Saransh App with the username and password sent via OTP and email.
- Data uploading: It enables the CBSE/schools to generate statistics in real time and to upload data.

Advantages of the Saransh App:

- Self-evaluation: It prepares parents and schools to evaluate students' performance in various subjects.
- Performance: It enables the school to examine academic performance at both the aggregate and individual student levels.
- Take action: Because it provides data-driven analysis, it enables parents and schools to make the best decisions for students.
- Communication: It improves communication and interactions between schools and parents.
- Information visualization: The measured values are presented in the form of numbers, charts, or

graphs, making it simple to review and comprehend.

- Information uploading: It enables the CBSE/schools to generate statistics in real-time and upload data.

Saransh GK app:

This is the GK Learning app, which covers all of the categories and areas for learning general knowledge quickly. Our goal is to educate children. Assisting children in expanding their general knowledge. Saransh GK app includes pictorial questions and descriptions

Conclusion:

Higher education in India has grown exponentially since its independence. While digitization stagehands in a new era of transparency, efficiency, and accountability, its proliferation in the field of education has brought about major changes with the possibility of completely changing the regular environment. With the advent of disruptive technology, new age start-ups have compelled teaching professionals to adapt to dynamic environments. Higher education in India has grown exponentially since its independence. Technology innovations that incorporate Cloud Computing and Mobile Apps have grown in popularity around the world as a catalyst for significant financial growth and citizen empowerment.

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